

ASHTEKAR VARIABLES FORMULATION OF GENERAL RELATIVITY

March 18, 2009

Abstract

A possible route towards a reformulation of General Relativity in terms of Ashtekar's connection variables is described. The (3+1)-decomposition is presented and then applied to complex General Relativity, where Ashtekar's variables are introduced. The Einstein Hilbert action and the Hamiltonian of complex General Relativity are presented in terms of connection variables. The constraints that follow from the variational principle and the reality conditions are discussed.

1 Introduction

General relativity is a gauge field theory in the sense that gravity is described by a $SO(1,3)$ connection. However, the requirement of the general covariance has made it quite different from ordinary gauge theories: the local gauge symmetry is intimately connected with space-time diffeomorphisms. Actually it is this feature that makes general relativity work as a theory of gravity. This difference gives rise to the serious problem of unrenormalizable divergences when one tries to construct a quantum theory of general relativity. It implies that the dynamics becomes more and more intricate as one goes to smaller scales. In the classical theory this does not cause any trouble because one can suppress local excitations. In contrast such a suppression is not possible in the quantum regime due to the existence of uncontrollable quantum fluctuations.

Attempts at constructing perturbative quantum gravity have been unsuccessful. It is generally believed that the problem lies in the basic assumption of perturbation theory that the real spacetime structure can be well approximated by a classical background geometry, even below the Planck scale. Nevertheless, quantum gravity may exist as an exact theory in spite of perturbation nonrenormalizability. The canonical quantization scheme does not require the fixation of a natural background geometry. The fact that the Hamiltonian structure of general relativity has certain essentially non-perturbative features - in the exact theory, the Hamiltonian is essentially given by the constraints, while the two decouple in any order in perturbation theory - suggests that qualitatively

new results may arise from exact canonical quantization. (Indeed as we will see Ashtekar variables are the key building block of loop quantum gravity.)

The dynamics of general relativity is generated by constraints. That is, the 6 Einstein equations describing time evolution can be obtained by calculating the Poisson brackets of the 3-metric and its conjugate momentum with a Hamiltonian that is a linear combination of constraints: quantities that must vanish on the physical phase space by the other 4 Einstein equations. While there are profound conceptual problems associated with quantizing gravity, many of the technical problems in canonical quantum gravity revolve around these constraints. In the early 1980s, Abhay Ashtekar and others developed 'new variables' to describe general relativity [14], [15], [3] in terms of which the constraints radically simplify. This eases the otherwise intractable factor-ordering problems one runs into when one tries to turn the constraints into operators in the process of canonical quantization. These new variables also bring the mathematical structure of general relativity much closer to that of Yang-Mills theory. As a result, one can apply techniques from gauge theory to quantum gravity.¹

In the late 1980s Lee Smolin and Carlo Rovelli, using the new variables, were able to devise a loop representation of quantum gravity [8], [12], [18] (where the key observables are Wilson loops). In this representation, states of quantum gravity correspond to isotopy invariants of 'generalized links', that is, collections of loops (not necessarily embedded) in space. This has led to the discovery of the intriguing relationships between quantum gravity and knot theory. The Chern-Simons state, for example, corresponds to the Kauffman bracket link invariant. It appears that these ideas can be used to construct many more solutions of the Wheeler-De Witt equation, as well. It seems, therefore, that gauge theories, knots and gravity are different facets of a single subject.

Although general relativity is clearly a gauge theory in some sense, the precise relation between general relativity and other gauge theories is no laughing matter. Certainly the notions of connection and curvature are crucial in general relativity, but in the original Einstein-Hilbert formulation they are derived from a more basic entity: the metric. For many years people have tried to invent formulations of general relativity in which the connection plays a more fundamental role and the metric is de-emphasized.

In the Palatini formalism, for example, the metric is a secondary concept, the basic fields being a Lorentz connection on the 'imitation tangent bundle' $M \times \mathbb{R}^n$ and a frame field $e : M \times \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow TM$. It is interesting to see what happens when one attempts to canonically quantize gravity using the Palatini formalism. Since there are more variables one expects more constraints. Indeed, one finds that in addition to the Hamiltonian and diffeomorphism constraints, there is a Gauß law constraint analogous to that in electromagnetism and Yang-Mills theory. The form of these constraints is much simpler than in the Einstein-

¹In particular, one can use Chern-Simons theory to obtain a solution of the Wheeler-DeWitt equation, $\hat{H}\psi = 0$, in the case of quantum gravity with a nonzero cosmological constant [20]. The physical significance - if any - of this 'Chern-Simons state' is still under investigation, as are its mathematical properties.

Hilbert approach. In particular, one can write the constraints so that they are polynomials (and spatial derivatives thereof) in terms of fields satisfying the canonical commutation relations. Unfortunately, the constraints are not closed under Poisson brackets. This complicates the quantization of the theory in such a way that the Palatini formalism is little better than the Einstein-Hilbert one for the purposes of quantum gravity. The 'new variables' can be thought of as a modification of the Palatini formalism that avoids this problem. The main idea is to take advantage of the special futures of 4-dimensional spacetime and work with the 'self-dual part' of the Lorentz connection.

Ashtekar and collaborators have written a couple of books [10], [17] summarizing the state of the art concerning canonical quantum gravity, particularly the new variables and the loop representation. The loop representation of quantum gravity was initiated in Lee Smolin and Carlo Rovelli's paper [12], and this is still a good place to begin the serious study of it. A very good review article on the loop representation is [19]. Throughout this dissertation we rely heavily on Domenico Giulini's lecture notes [1]. This is because Giulini's presentation of the subject is the most thorough one, and his - somewhat idiosyncratic - notation makes calculations more straightforward. No use of spinors is made here, unlike Ashtekar's book and his original article [3]. In most of the literature nowadays [4], [5], [7] exterior curvature and the Gauß-Godazzi equations are used as a starting point for the reformulation of general relativity in terms of Ashtekar's variables. The intuitive visualization of our subject does become clearer with this notation, and that's why the second main reference of this dissertation is Baez's and Muniain's book, which emphasizes geometrical concepts rather than detailed derivations [2].²

2 Notation

Let M be a connected orientable and time orientable Lorentz 4-manifold with topology $\Sigma \times \mathbf{R}$, where Σ can be any connected orientable 3-manifold. We

²There's an old maths joke that goes like this: differential geometry is that portion of mathematics which remains invariant under change of notation. Even though this phenomenon usually causes confusion to the outsider, and dogmatism to the insider, it also exhibits an analogy to the fact that certain aspects of general relativity (like that it is a gauge theory) can be better understood when the theory is reformulated with different variables; pushing this line of thought to its limit, what if quantum gravity is that portion of theoretical physics which remains invariant under change of theory? (eg. string theory, loop quantum gravity, supergravity etc.)

Going through the tedious drill of re-expressing the same-ol' mathematical and physical ideas, through ever-changing names, notations, assumptions, variables, post-doctoral placements, and whatnot, every now and then may actually help us develop a practical skill: to see the global idea lying beyond the local conventions of each sect of academicians. The importance of such a skill cannot be underestimated. Especially these days that, according to Smolin [9], the sociology and group-think of the theoretical physics community is blocking the very progress of quantum gravity research. Furthermore, this not-to-miss-the-forest-for-the-tree skill is highly transferable; it can be used equally well in the search for the holy grail of physics, as for socio-political analyses or deciphering dead languages (in case some theoretical physicist is crazy enough to consider a change of career).

use the signature convention $(-, +, +, +)$. Greek indices refer to coordinate bases, latin indices to frame bases. If they are taken from the beginning of the alphabet, i.e. $(\alpha, \beta, \dots; a, b, \dots)$, their range is $\{0, 1, 2, 3\}$, whereas for the middle of the alphabet, i.e. $(\mu, \nu, \dots; i, j, \dots)$, their range is only $\{1, 2, 3\}$. Einstein's summation convention is used throughout. Square brackets around a string of n indices denote full antisymmetrization including the factor $1/n!$. In the same way, round brackets denote symmetrization. The Lorentz metric is denoted by g . η_{ab} denotes the matrix $\text{diag}(-1, 1, 1, 1)$. Indices of tensors are lowered by contraction with η_{ab} , and raised by contraction with η^{ab} . The components of the curvature tensor are written R^a_{bcd} , $R_{ab} = R^c_{acb}$ are the components of the Ricci-tensor and $R = g^{ab}R_{ab}$ denotes the Ricci scalar.

The structure group for the real frame bundle on M is $GL(4, R)$, and $SO(1, 3)$ if one restricts to orthonormal frames. This restriction is equivalent to imposing an orientation and a metric structure, and will be adopted throughout the text. We denote the Lie algebra of $SO(1, 3)$ by $so(1, 3)$. Due to the assumption that M is topologically $\Sigma \times \mathbb{R}$ and orientable the frame bundle is necessarily trivial so that we can always assume the existence of a globally defined tetrad. This is also true if one considers the complexified tangent bundle, which we shall need later on. Let $\{e_a\}$ be the orthonormal tetrad and $\{e^a\}$ its dual co-tetrad, so that $g(e_a, e_b) = \eta_{ab}$ and $e^a(e_b) = \delta_b^a$. The volume form ϵ on M induced by g is given by

$$\epsilon = e^0 \wedge e^1 \wedge e^2 \wedge e^3 = \frac{1}{4!} \epsilon_{abcd} e^a \wedge e^b \wedge e^c \wedge e^d, \quad (1)$$

where

$$\epsilon_{abcd} = 4! \delta_{[a}^0 \delta_b^1 \delta_c^2 \delta_{d]}^3. \quad (2)$$

Once we have restricted the structure group to $SO(1, 3)$ we also restrict the connection to be metric-preserving. The connection 1-form can be represented by a globally defined $so(1, 3)$ -valued 1-form ω_b^a , and the curvature by an $so(1, 3)$ -valued 2-form Ω_b^a . If ∇ denotes the covariant derivative, one has

$$\nabla_{e_a} e_b = \omega_b^c(e_a) e_c \quad (3)$$

$$\eta_{ac} \omega_b^c \equiv \omega_{ab} = -\omega_{ba}, \quad (4)$$

and

$$(\nabla_{e_a} \nabla_{e_b} - \nabla_{e_b} \nabla_{e_a} - \nabla_{[e_a, e_b]}) e_c = \Omega_c^d(e_a, e_b) e_d = R^d_{cab} e_d \quad (5)$$

$$\eta_{ac} \Omega_b^c \equiv \Omega_{ab} = -\Omega_{ba}. \quad (6)$$

Let V denote a vector space that carries a representation, ρ , of $SO(1, 3)$, and λ a V -valued n -form on M which under change of tetrads transforms via ρ . Then the exterior covariant derivative, D , on vector-valued forms is defined via

$$D\lambda \equiv d\lambda + \rho(\omega) \wedge \lambda, \quad (7)$$

so that

$$D^2\lambda = \rho(\Omega) \wedge \lambda. \quad (8)$$

Here the symbol $\rho(\omega) \wedge \lambda$ is to be understood in the following way: The representation ρ of $SO(1,3)$ on V induces a representation of its Lie algebra $so(1,3)$ on V , which we also denote by ρ . Via this representation ω ($so(1,3)$ -valued) acts on λ (V -valued), while as forms the exterior product is taken.

The Hodge-duality map \star , provides a linear isomorphism between n forms and $(4-n)$ -forms at each point on M . It can be defined via

$$\star(e^{a_1} \wedge \dots \wedge e^{a_n}) = \frac{1}{(4-n)!} \epsilon^{a_1 \dots a_n a_{n+1} \dots a_4} e^{a_{n+1}} \wedge \dots \wedge e^{a_4}, \quad (9)$$

and linear extension, where the indices on ϵ are raised using η^{ab} . Applying \star twice results in plus or minus the identity. In fact, on any n -form λ one has

$$\star(\star\lambda) = -(-1)^{n(4-n)}\lambda. \quad (10)$$

Analogous formulae hold in any spacetime dimensions. Here, the first minus sign on the right hand side of eq.(10) is the sign of the determinant of η_{ab} . In four dimensions and Lorentz signature, \star squares to -1 on 2-forms, so that eigenforms only exist on the complexified tangent bundle with eigenvalues $+i$ (self-dual 2-forms) and $-i$ (anti-self-dual 2-forms). Given two n -forms λ and σ at some point in M :

$$\lambda = \frac{1}{n!} \lambda_{a_1 \dots a_n} e^{a_1} \wedge \dots \wedge e^{a_n}, \quad (11)$$

$$\sigma = \frac{1}{n!} \sigma_{a_1 \dots a_n} e^{a_1} \wedge \dots \wedge e^{a_n}, \quad (12)$$

we define their inner product, induced by g , via

$$\langle \lambda, \sigma \rangle = \frac{1}{n!} \lambda_{a_1 \dots a_n} g^{a_1 b_1} \dots g^{a_n b_n} \sigma_{b_1 \dots b_n} = \lambda_{a_1 \dots a_n} \sigma^{a_1 \dots a_n}, \quad (13)$$

and have

$$\lambda \wedge \star\sigma = \langle \lambda, \sigma \rangle \epsilon. \quad (14)$$

3 Complex General Relativity

We now consider the complexified tensor bundle

$$T_C = \bigoplus_{r,s} T_s^r(M) \otimes C, \quad (15)$$

over the real manifold M . Here $T_s^r(M)$ denotes the (real) tensor bundle of r -fold contravariant and s -fold covariant tensors over M . The structure group is $SO(1,3)_C \cong SO(4)_C$. The fields e^a , ω_b^a , Ω_b^a , T^a and η_{ab} extend to sections in the complexified bundle. The variational principle and the resulting equations of motion transcribe verbatim from (real) General Relativity, with all quantities now being complex. The theory so obtained may be called complex General Relativity. Since the complex tensor bundle is obtained by complexification of a real tensor bundle, we can speak of real sections in it.

On the space of complex 2-forms, we can now consider eigenforms to the \star -operator (since $\star^2 = -1$)

$$\star\lambda = i\lambda \quad \text{self-dual} \quad (16)$$

$$\star\lambda = -i\lambda \quad \text{anti-self-dual}. \quad (17)$$

Similarly in the complexified Lie algebra $so(1,3)_C$, we can define a dualization operation (denoted by \star):

$$\star\sigma_{ab} \equiv \frac{1}{2}\epsilon_{ab}{}^{cd}\sigma_{cd} \quad (18)$$

that also squares to minus the identity and thus decomposes the complexified Lie algebra into self- and anti-self-dual parts.

4 The 3 + 1 decomposition

4.1 Metric decomposition

Let $M \cong R \times \Sigma$ be foliated by the images of a one-parameter family of embeddings, $E_t : \Sigma \rightarrow M$, and let Σ_t denote the image of Σ under E_t in M .

Fig. 1. Slices of the spacetime $\mathbb{R} \times S^1$ [2]

We have the following vector field over E_t :

$$\partial_t \equiv \frac{d}{dt} E_t \quad p \mapsto \frac{d}{dt} E_t(p) \in T_{E_t(p)}(M), \quad (19)$$

whose spacetime interpretation is to generate the motion of Σ through M . We decompose it with respect to an orthonormal tetrad $\{n, e_k\}$ which is adapted to the foliation. We will use a \perp for the zeroth frame index and t for the zeroth coordinate to distinguish the two and to remind on the special choice made, but to avoid unnecessary confusion in this section n stands for e_\perp . The dual co-tetrad is $\{n', e^k\}$ (where $n' = e^\perp$). We now have:

$$\partial_t = Nn + N^k e_k, \quad (20)$$

where N and $N^k e_k$ are the so-called lapse function and shift vector field respectively.

Fig. 2. Splitting ∂_t into normal and tangential components [2]

Let further $\{x^\mu\}$ be a coordinate system on Σ so that $\{t, x^\mu\}$ is an adapted coordinate system on M and where ∂_t is given by eq.(20). The relation between the spatial coordinate and frame bases is given by

$$\partial_\mu = e_\mu^k e_k, \quad e_k = e_k^\mu \partial_\mu \quad (21)$$

where $\{e_\mu^k\}$ and $\{e_k^\mu\}$ are relative inverse matrices. To sum up, we have (N^μ denote the components of the shift vector with respect to the coordinate basis)

$$\partial_t = Nn + N^k e_k \quad (22)$$

$$\partial_\mu = e_\mu^k e_k \quad (23)$$

$$n = \frac{1}{N}\partial_t - \frac{N^\mu}{N}\partial_\mu \quad (24)$$

$$e_k = e_k^\mu \partial_\mu \quad (25)$$

and

$$dt = \frac{n'}{N} \quad (26)$$

$$dx^\mu = -\frac{N^\mu}{N}n' + e_k^\mu e^k \quad (27)$$

$$n' = N dt \quad (28)$$

$$e^k = N^k dt + e_\mu^k dx^\mu \quad (29)$$

The four-dimensional Lorentz metric

$$ds^2 = \eta_{ab}e^a \otimes e^b = g_{\alpha\beta}dx^\alpha \otimes dx^\beta \quad (30)$$

decomposes as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \eta_{\alpha\beta}e^a \otimes e^b &= -n' \otimes n' + e^k \otimes e^l \delta_{kl} \\ &= -N^2 dt \otimes dt + \delta_{kl}(N^k dt + e_\mu^k dx^\mu) \otimes (N^l dt + e_\nu^l dx^\nu) \end{aligned} \quad (31)$$

where the coordinate components of the spatial part are given by

$$h_{\mu\nu} = e^k \otimes e^l \delta_{kl}(\partial_\mu, \partial_\nu) = e_\mu^k e_\nu^l \delta_{kl} \quad (32)$$

$$h^{\mu\nu} = \delta^{kl} e_k^\mu e_l^\nu \quad (33)$$

$$e_\mu^k = h_{\mu\nu} \delta^{kl} e_l^\nu \quad (34)$$

$$e_k^\mu = h^{\mu\nu} \delta_{kl} e_\nu^l \quad (35)$$

We can write the Lorentz metric in the form:

$$\begin{aligned} g_{\alpha\beta}dx^\alpha \otimes dx^\beta &= -n \otimes n + e_k \otimes e_l \delta^{kl} = \eta_{\alpha\beta}e^\alpha \otimes e^\beta \\ &= (-N^2 + \delta_{kl}N^k N^l)dt \otimes dt + \delta_{kl}N^k e_\mu^l dt \otimes dx^\mu + \delta_{kl}e_\mu^k N^l dx^\mu \otimes dt + \delta_{kl}e_\mu^k e_\nu^l dx^\mu \otimes dx^\nu \\ &= -(N^2 + N^l N_l)dt \otimes dt + N_l e_\mu^l dt \otimes dx^\mu + N_k e_\mu^k dx^\mu \otimes dt + \delta_{kl}e_\mu^k e_\nu^l dx^\mu \otimes dx^\nu \end{aligned}$$

$$= -(N^2 + N^l N_l) dt \otimes dt + N_k e_\mu^k (dt \otimes dx^\mu + dx^\mu \otimes dt) + h_{\mu\nu} dx^\mu \otimes dx^\nu \quad (36)$$

The inverse of the Lorentz metric can be written in the form:

$$\begin{aligned} g^{\alpha\beta} \partial_\alpha \otimes \partial_\beta &= -\eta^{ab} e_a \otimes e_b = -n' \otimes n' + \delta_{kl} e^k \otimes e^l \\ &= -\left(\frac{1}{N} \partial_t - \frac{N^\mu}{N} \partial_\mu\right) \otimes \left(\frac{1}{N} \partial_t - \frac{N^\nu}{N} \partial_\nu\right) + \delta^{kl} (e_k^\mu \partial_\mu) \otimes (e_l^\nu \partial_\nu) \\ &= -\frac{1}{N^2} \partial_t \otimes \partial_t + \frac{N^\nu}{N^2} N^\nu \partial_t \otimes \partial_\nu + \frac{N^\mu}{N^2} \partial_\mu \otimes \partial_t - \frac{N^\mu N^\nu}{N^2} \partial_\mu \otimes \partial_\nu + \delta^{kl} e_k^\mu e_l^\nu \partial_\mu \otimes \partial_\nu \\ &= -\frac{1}{N^2} \partial_t \otimes \partial_t + (h^{\mu\nu} - \frac{N^\mu N^\nu}{N^2}) \partial_\mu \otimes \partial_\nu + \frac{N^\mu}{N^2} (\partial_\mu \otimes \partial_t + \partial_t \otimes \partial_\mu) \end{aligned} \quad (37)$$

4.2 Action decomposition

The Einstein-Hilbert action is:

$$\int \Omega_{ab} \wedge \star(e^a \wedge e^b) = \int R \epsilon \quad (38)$$

where ϵ is the volume form on M induced by g . The vanishing variation of eq.(38) with respect to the co-tetrad e^a , yields the vacuum Einstein field equations:

$$R_{ab} - \frac{1}{2} \eta_{ab} R = 0. \quad (39)$$

Following the standard route, we will put the Einstein-Hilbert action into Hamiltonian form, and decompose the co-tetrad variables according to eqs (26), (27) i.e., we will use the variables

$$(e_\mu^k, N^\mu, N) \quad (40)$$

A first step in arriving at an algebraically simpler form of the Hamiltonian action integral is to take the frame rather than co-frame components as variables and redefine these variables by partially densitizing them (i.e multiplying by powers of \sqrt{h} , where h is the determinant of the 3-metric). The new variables are:

$$E_k^\mu \equiv \sqrt{h} e_k^\mu = \frac{1}{\det\{e_k^\mu\}} e_k^\mu \quad (41)$$

$$N'^\mu \equiv N^\mu, \quad (42)$$

$$N' \equiv \frac{1}{\sqrt{h}}N = \det\{e_k^\mu\}N. \quad (43)$$

We want to write the Einstein-Hilbert action in 3+1-decomposed form using the densitized variables just introduced. From now on E_k^μ are the components of a triad of density weight-one, N^μ is a spatial vector field and N is a spatial scalar of density weight minus one. The action integrand then decomposes as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega_{ab} \wedge \star(e^a \wedge e^b) &= \frac{1}{2}R_{ab\alpha\beta}dx^\alpha \wedge dx^\beta \wedge \star(e^a \wedge e^b) = \frac{1}{2}R_{ab\alpha\beta} \langle dx^\alpha \wedge dx^\beta, e^a \wedge e^b \rangle \\ &= \frac{1}{2}R_{ab\alpha\beta}E_c^\alpha E_d^\beta \langle e^c \wedge e^d, e^a \wedge e^b \rangle = \frac{1}{h}\epsilon = R_{\alpha\beta}^{cd}E_c^\alpha E_d^\beta N dt d^3x \end{aligned}$$

5 3+1-Decomposition of Self-Dual Action in Ashtekar's Variables

5.1 Hamiltonian decomposition

From now on we only consider complex General Relativity with self dual action. We omit the (+) on $(^+)\omega$ and simply write ω for the self dual connection. We define

$$i\epsilon_{nm}^k \lambda^n \sigma^m = (\vec{\lambda} \times \vec{\sigma})^k \quad (44)$$

$$\vec{A}_\mu = \vec{\omega}_\mu \quad (45)$$

$$\vec{\Lambda} = -2\vec{\omega}_t \quad (46)$$

and have

$$\vec{F}_{\mu\nu} = (d\vec{A} + \frac{1}{2}\vec{A} \times \vec{A})_{\mu\nu} \quad (47)$$

$$R^{\perp k}{}_{t\nu} = \frac{1}{2}(\partial_t A_\nu^k + D_\nu \Lambda^k) \quad (48)$$

$$R^{\perp k}{}_{\mu\nu} = \frac{1}{2}F_{\mu\nu}^k \quad (49)$$

$$R^{kl}{}_{\mu\nu} = -i\frac{1}{2}\epsilon^{kl}{}_p F_{\mu\nu}^p \quad (50)$$

We also abbreviate $(E_1^\mu, E_2^\mu, E_3^\mu) = \vec{E}^\mu$ and regard the action as a functional in the variables $\vec{A}_\mu, \vec{E}^\mu, N$ and N^μ . These are Ashtekar's variables, or connection

variables, since \vec{A}_μ is a connection 1-form for a $SO(3)_C$ -connection over the 3-dimensional manifold Σ . Using the above relations we can write the complex action in the following form:

$$\begin{aligned}
S &= \int (-N i \frac{1}{2} \epsilon^{kl} {}_p F_{\mu\nu}^p E_k^\mu E_l^\nu - 2N^\mu \frac{1}{2} F_{\mu\nu}^k E_k^\nu + 2 \frac{1}{2} (\partial_t A_\nu^k + D_\nu \Lambda^k) E_k^\nu) dt d^3x \\
&= \int (-N \frac{1}{2} F_{\mu\nu}^p (i \epsilon^{kl} {}_p E_k^\mu E_l^\nu) - N^\mu F_{\mu\nu}^k E_k^\nu + (\partial_t A_\nu^k + D_\nu \Lambda^k) E_k^\nu) dt d^3x \\
&= \int (-\frac{1}{2} N \vec{F}_{\mu\nu} \cdot (\vec{E}^\mu \times \vec{E}^\nu) - N^\mu \vec{F}_{\mu\nu} \cdot \vec{E}^\nu + (\partial_t \vec{A}_\nu) \cdot \vec{E}^\nu + (D_\nu \vec{\Lambda}) \cdot \vec{E}^\nu) dt d^3x
\end{aligned} \tag{51}$$

We apply the Leibniz rule

$$(D_\mu \vec{\Lambda}) \cdot \vec{E}^\mu = D_\mu (\vec{\Lambda} \cdot \vec{E}^\mu) - \vec{\Lambda} \cdot (D_\mu \vec{E}^\mu) \tag{52}$$

and integrate by parts without keeping the last term³

$$\int (D_\mu \vec{\Lambda}) \cdot \vec{E}^\mu dt d^3x = - \int \vec{\Lambda} \cdot (D_\mu \vec{E}^\mu) dt d^3x \tag{53}$$

Therefore

$$S = \int \{ (\partial_t A_\nu) \cdot E^\nu - [\frac{1}{2} N \vec{F}_{\mu\nu} \cdot (\vec{E}^\mu \times \vec{E}^\nu) + N^\mu \vec{F}_{\mu\nu} \cdot \vec{E}^\nu + \vec{\Lambda} \cdot (D_\mu \vec{E}^\mu)] \} dt d^3x \tag{54}$$

The action is now seen to be already in Hamiltonian form, i.e., of the form

$$\int (\dot{q}p - H(q, p)) dt \tag{55}$$

thus identifying the canonical conjugate pair of variables as

$$(\vec{A}_\mu, \vec{E}^\mu) \tag{56}$$

and the Hamiltonian

$$\mathcal{H} = \int_\Sigma \{ \frac{1}{2} N \vec{F}_{\mu\nu} \cdot (\vec{E}^\mu \times \vec{E}^\nu) + N^\mu \vec{F}_{\mu\nu} \cdot \vec{E}^\nu + \vec{\Lambda} \cdot (D_\mu \vec{E}^\mu) \} d^3x \tag{57}$$

³The last term is turned into a surface term through Gauß law; if Σ is closed, this term vanishes: $\int D_\mu (\vec{\Lambda} \cdot \vec{E}^\mu) dt d^3x = \int_\Sigma \vec{\Lambda} \cdot \vec{E}^\mu d^3x = 0$

5.2 The new variables

The field playing the role analogous to the “position” in classical mechanics is now the self-dual Lorentz connection \vec{A}_μ on space, rather than the 3-metric. The momentum conjugate to \vec{A}_μ turns out to be \vec{E}^μ . The components of \vec{E}^μ are $E_k^\mu \equiv \sqrt{h}e_k^\mu$, where h is the determinant of the 3-metric, and we have the Poisson bracket relations:

$$\{E_k^\mu(x), A_\nu^l(y)\} = -i\delta_\nu^\mu\delta_k^l\delta^{(3)}(x, y) \quad (58)$$

$$\{E_k^\mu(x), E_l^\nu(y)\} = 0 \quad (59)$$

$$\{A_\mu^k(x), A_\nu^l(y)\} = 0 \quad (60)$$

where x and y are coordinates on Σ .

To quantize, we replace the classical “position” and “momentum” variables \vec{A}_μ and \vec{E}^μ by the operators

$$(\hat{\vec{A}}_\mu(x)\psi)(\vec{A}) = \vec{A}_\mu(x)\psi(\vec{A}) \quad (61)$$

and

$$(\hat{\vec{E}}^\mu(x)\psi)(\vec{A}) = \frac{\partial}{\partial \vec{A}_\mu(x)}\psi(\vec{A}), \quad (62)$$

which have commutation relations

$$[\hat{E}_k^\mu(x), \hat{A}_\nu^l(y)] = \delta_\nu^\mu\delta_k^l\delta^{(3)}(x, y) \quad (63)$$

$$[\hat{E}_k^\mu(x), \hat{E}_l^\nu(y)] = 0 \quad (64)$$

$$[\hat{A}_\mu^k(x), \hat{A}_\nu^l(y)] = 0 \quad (65)$$

analogous to the classical Poisson bracket relations.⁴

⁴While the field redefinition above is faithful locally on the configuration space of the three dimensional metric tensor, it introduces new periodicities (the Wilson loops of all gauge fields take values in the space of complex units) and quantization laws that cannot be derived from the metric itself. In loop quantum gravity, these are manifested as the area quantization rules. These rules do not follow from the metric tensor and its quantization, but rather from the special global properties of Ashtekar’s field redefinition. A different field redefinition could “predict” the quantization of other quantities than the area.

6 Constraints

If we vary the action with respect to the fields N , N^μ and $\vec{\Lambda}$ we obtain equations in the canonical variables without time derivatives, that is, we obtain the constraints:

$$H = \frac{1}{2} \vec{F}_{\mu\nu} \cdot (\vec{E}^\mu \times \vec{E}^\nu) = 0 \quad (66)$$

$$H_\mu = \vec{F}_{\mu\nu} \cdot \vec{E}^\nu = 0 \quad (67)$$

$$\vec{H} = D_\mu \vec{E}^\mu = 0 \quad (68)$$

The Hamiltonian is just the sum of smeared constraints with the smearing functions N , N^μ and $\vec{\Lambda}$:

$$\mathcal{H} = \int_{\Sigma} \{NH + N^\mu H_\mu + \vec{\Lambda} \cdot \vec{H}\} d^3x \quad (69)$$

While we will not go into the details, it is absolutely crucial that these constraints are closed under Poisson brackets. It is also important to note the relationship between general relativity and Yang Mills theory that follows from the above facts. The field \vec{E}^μ plays the part of the electric field in Yang-Mills theory, while $\vec{F}_{\mu\nu}$ plays the part of the magnetic field. The Gauß law $\vec{H} = 0$ for gravity in the new variables format is identical to that for the Yang-Mills equations, but the Hamiltonian and diffeomorphism constraints are new, as is the fact that time evolution is generated by constraints.

7 Reality conditions

In the complex canonical theory the dynamical degrees of freedom for the gravitational fields are doubled compared with the real triad formalism. Hence in order for the theory to be equivalent to the original Einstein theory, some additional constraints should be imposed. So far we have merely reformulated complex General Relativity. But, of course, ultimately we are interested in the ordinary real case. A central question therefore is how to recover the real theory within the formalism developed, that is, how to derive a real 3-metric from the complex equations of motion for \vec{A}_μ and \vec{E}^μ with real lapse and shift functions N and N^μ . In the real case it is also easy to give some geometric interpretation to the variables \vec{A}_μ and \vec{E}^μ .

As outlined in section 3, we are working on complex tensor bundles with reality structure. Real sections have real component functions with respect to real bases and real bases are provided since we work on a real manifold. Note that we only require the 3-metric and not the (densitized) tetrad to be real. The former is derived from the latter according to:

$$h^{\mu\nu} = \frac{1}{h} \vec{E}^\mu \cdot \vec{E}^\nu \delta_{\mu\nu}, \quad (70)$$

so that

$$h^{\mu\nu} = [\det\{\vec{E}^\mu \cdot \vec{E}^\nu\}]^{-\frac{1}{2}} \vec{E}^\mu \cdot \vec{E}^\nu. \quad (71)$$

If we suppose that $\vec{E}^\mu \cdot \vec{E}^\nu$, N and N^μ are real, the Hamiltonian flow and the diffeomorphism generator do not disturb this reality; the gauge generator Poisson-commutes with $\vec{E}^\mu \cdot \vec{E}^\nu$ and therefore drops out of discussion. The reality condition that results from calculating the Poisson bracket of $\vec{E}^\mu \cdot \vec{E}^\nu$ with the scalar constraint NH is:

$$(\vec{E}^\sigma \times D_\sigma \vec{E}^\mu) \cdot \vec{E}^\nu = \text{real}. \quad (72)$$

One may check that there are no further constraints, i.e. the Poisson bracket of this expression with the Hamiltonian is real due to the reality conditions already posed. So the Hamiltonian flow preserves reality, provided the initial data are further constrained by the reality of $h_{\mu\nu}$ and eq.(72).⁵

8 Geometric interpretation of the canonical variables

8.1 Momenta \vec{E}^μ

Eq.(70) can be written in the form

$$h h^{\mu\nu} = \vec{E}^\mu \cdot \vec{E}^\nu \quad (73)$$

where $h = \det\{h_{\mu\nu}\}$ and consider e.g. the 3-3 component of this equation. The left hand side is just the subteterminant $h_{11}h_{22} - h_{12}^2$ which for real $h_{\mu\nu}$ measures the area content of the parallelogram in tangent-space spanned by the vectors ∂_1 and ∂_2 . The area content of an embedded 2-surface (coordinatized by σ and τ):

$$(\sigma, \tau) \mapsto x^\mu(\sigma, \tau), \quad (74)$$

is thus given by (no summation convention here):

$$\int \sum_{\lambda, \mu, \nu} \sqrt{\vec{E}^\lambda \cdot \vec{E}^\lambda \varepsilon_{\lambda\mu\nu}} \frac{\partial x^\mu}{\partial \tau} \frac{\partial x^\nu}{\partial \sigma} d\tau d\sigma, \quad (75)$$

⁵The Lorentzian hamiltonian constraint does not have a simple polynomial form if we use the real connection. For a while, this fact was considered an obstacle to defining the quantum hamiltonian constraint; therefore the complex version of the connection was mostly used. However, Thiemann [13], [11] has recently succeeded in constructing a Lorentzian quantum hamiltonian constraint in spite of the non-polynomiality of the classical expression. This is the reason why the real connection is now widely used. This choice has the advantage of eliminating the old “reality conditions” problem, namely the problem of implementing non-trivial reality conditions in the quantum theory.

where the integral is taken over the surface. $\varepsilon_{\lambda\mu\nu}$ denotes the 3-form density on Σ of weight -1, whose components in all coordinate systems are 0 if two indices coincide and ± 1 if they form an even, respectively odd permutation of 123. In that sense the variables \vec{E}^μ are geometrically connected to areas, rather than length.⁶

8.2 Position \vec{A}_μ

Here we use ω for the connection 1-form and $^{(+)}\omega$ for the self-dual part, and have

$$A_\mu^k = 2^{(+)}\omega_\mu^k = -i\frac{1}{2}\epsilon^{\perp k}{}_{lm}(\omega_\mu^{lm} - i\epsilon^{lm}{}_{\perp p}\omega_\mu^{\perp p}). \quad (77)$$

If the equations of motion are satisfied we have $\omega = \Gamma$, the Levi-Civita connection. Correspondingly let the covariant derivative on spacetime be $^{(4)}\nabla$ and the induced space covariant derivative on Σ (compatible with $h_{\mu\nu}$) be $^{(3)}\nabla$. The definition of extrinsic curvature is:

$$^{(4)}\nabla_{e_k} e_l \equiv ^{(3)}\nabla_{e_k} e_l + K_{kl} n \quad (78)$$

and have

$$\omega_\mu^{\perp k} = K_\mu^k = \delta^{kl} e_\mu^i K_{il}. \quad (79)$$

Inserting this into eq.(77) yields

$$A_\mu^k = \Gamma_\mu^k + K_\mu^k, \quad (80)$$

where

$$\Gamma_\mu^k \equiv -i\frac{1}{2}\epsilon^{\perp k}{}_{ln}\Gamma_\mu^{ln}. \quad (81)$$

The spatial components, Γ_μ^{ln} , are the components for the Levi-Civita connection on Σ compatible with $h_{\mu\nu}$. Relation (80) shows the non-triviality of the transformation to the connection variables: the connection 1-form \vec{A} involves the metric

⁶In bosonic string theory, the space-time embedding of a string world sheet is described by functions $X^\alpha(\sigma, \tau)$. The string sigma-model action, or Polyakov action, is expressed in terms of an auxiliary worldsheet metric $h_{ab}(\sigma, \tau)$. If we use the notation h_{ab} for the worldsheet metric, whereas $g_{\alpha\beta}$ is the metric of the target manifold (spacetime) and T is the string tension, the Polyakov action is

$$S = -\frac{1}{2}T \int \sqrt{-h} h^{ab} g_{\alpha\beta} \frac{\partial X^\alpha(\sigma)}{\partial x^a} \frac{\partial X^\beta(\sigma)}{\partial x^b} d^2\sigma \quad (76)$$

The Polyakov action is more convenient for quantization than the (equivalent at the classical level) Nambu-Goto action, because it is linear [16].

Although quite tempting, any analogies between eqs (75) and (38) should not be taken too far; in eq.(75) the target manifold is 3-dimensional space while in eq.(38) it is 4-dimensional spacetime; only the square term of eq.(75) has some formal similarity to eq.(38); and while both σ and τ in eq.(75) are spacelike coordinates, in (38) σ is timelike and τ is spacelike.

and the extrinsic curvature and therefore both conjugate sets of variables of the metric formulation.

9 Conclusion

We considered complex general relativity, and presented the (3+1)-decomposition of the self dual metric, action and hamiltonian. We applied the decomposition to complex general relativity, and introduced Ashtekar's connection variables. The Hamiltonian of complex general relativity was presented in terms of connection variables. We discussed the reality conditions that have to be imposed by hand to select real solutions, and briefly sketched the geometric interpretation of the new variables.

What was achieved is a description of the classical reformulation of general relativity in Ashtekar's variables. The purpose of this reformulation is of course the quantization of general relativity. Such an ambitious task is beyond the scope of this dissertation, and is currently a rapidly developing field of research, since Ashtekar's variables are the key building block of loop quantum gravity.

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